

REASON – A Proposed Research Commons for Norway

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Together with 13 national and international project partner organizations, in November 2023 UiT The Arctic University of Norway and the DataverseNO consortium submitted a major proposal for funding from the Norwegian Research Council to establish a **ResEArch Commons fOr Norway** (REASON). REASON is a proposed generalist research infrastructure for Norway which complements and supplements domain-specific / specialized infrastructures and includes the essential elements of the new Global Open Research Commons (GORC) Model recently published by the Research Data Alliance (RDA) (Woodford et al. 2023), as outlined in the figure below.

Rationale: Why build REASON

Research Commons are now seen as an internationally recognized model for delivery of integrated research services and are being designed globally at the institutional, national and European level. REASON will bring together and enrich formerly insufficiently or unconnected research infrastructure components in Norway, including domain-specific components.

Rationale: Why use the GORC Model

The GORC Model was developed through a rigorous year+ project by a group of global experts under the auspices of the leading research data organization, the Research Data Alliance (RDA). It provides a fully developed and well documented reference template for building research commons; is comprehensive, and covers all aspects of a research commons, including technical, governance and policy; is designed around facilitation of the FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles.

Rationale: Why the timing is right

The availability of the GORC Model provides for the first time a globally accepted template for research commons. The national repository DataverseNO, RSpace for active data management, iRODS for policy-based data management, data management plans, and Diamond Open Access publishing services combine to provide most of the essential technical elements needed in a Research Commons. Dataverse is already integrated with RSpace and iRODS, both of which are enthusiastic participants in this proposal. The Norwegian research organizations involved in providing DataverseNO collectively possess (a) an understanding of the research infrastructure in Norway; and (b) relationships with the organizations involved in providing the infrastructure needed to progress development of the REASON. A broad range of relevant expertise, experience and connections is brought to bear by other participants in the proposal.

Technical Core of REASON

The REASON infrastructure will consist of the nine essential elements of the GORC Model outlined above. The *services and tools* element focuses on enabling end user functionalities. It will bring together Research Objects (ROs) with cloud computing and storage infrastructure and software, services and applications for managing, analyzing and sharing ROs to create an integrated set of interoperable and complementary research resources, as outlined in the figure below.

A model/reference for other countries?

The developers of the REASON proposal believe that REASON could serve as a useful model/reference for others developing research commons, and are interested in information exchange and possible collaboration. Please feel to contact us at philipp.conzett@uit.no.

References

REASON = Research Commons for Norway. Proposal submitted to the Norwegian Financing Initiative for Research Infrastructure (INFRASTRUKTUR) in November 2023. Project partner organizations: UiT The Arctic University of Norway (project owner), The Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU), NTNU – Norwegian University of Science and Technology, University of Bergen, University of Oslo, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS), DataCite, Forschungszentrum Jülich, Harvard University, KU Leuven, Research Space, Simon Fraser University, Syracuse University, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Woodford, C., Treloar, A., Leggott, M., Jones, S., Lopez Albacete, J., Madalli, D., Genova, F., Dharmawardena, K., Chibhira, N., Åkerström, W. N., Macneil, R., Nurnberger, A., Pfeiffenberger, H., Tanifuji, M., Zhang, Q., Jones, N., Sesink, L., Wood-Charlson, E., & RDA GORC International Model WG. (2023). The Global Open Research Commons International Model, Version 1 (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00099>